

Analysis and Diagnosis of ITSC in Dual Rotor Air-Cored PMSG - Parallel Connected Stator Coils

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Abstract—Inter-turn short circuits (ITSCs) stands as one of the most challenging faults to detect in permanent magnet synchronous machines (PMSMs). This study focusses on a dual-rotor, air-cored permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) with parallel-connected coils. For the analysis of the ITSC, a finite element analysis (FEA) model has been developed and validated under healthy conditions. In order to investigate the impact of ITSC faults on the PMSG and to understand the progression of fault severity, multiple cases with varying levels of fault intensity were analyzed and validated using mathematical modeling. The severity of the fault depends on two key parameters: the contact resistance and the number of shorted turns. To detect ITSCs in PMSMs, current-based methods are commonly employed, particularly because these machines are typically connected to PWM-based power electronic converters. In this study, motor current signature analysis (MCSA) and the extended park's vector approach (EPVA) were implemented. However, both methods faced challenges in detecting low-severity faults as a result to the generator's low operating frequency. This findings showcases the necessity for alternative diagnostic strategies to detect the ITSC under low fault severity.

Index Terms—Condition monitoring, fault diagnosis, permanent magnet generator, Stator faults.

I. INTRODUCTION

A rising demand for energy conversion with low power consumption has led to the introduction of direct-drive Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generators (PMSGs) in wind, tidal and wave power applications. Specifically, the [1] C-GEN generator is a lightweight, coreless stator with modular construction ideally suited for harsh marine environments. The high torque density and simplified mechanical integration are key features that reduce system complexity and maintenance costs.

All these advantages aside, electrical faults remain a major problem in PMSGs. ITSCs are the product of the degradation of the insulation between two or turns of the same phase.

This work has been supported by the EU HORIZON and UKRI project entitled: "MEGA PTO WAVE", EU HORIZON project ID: 101147321.

This fault may lead to a catastrophic breakdown, as it induces localized overheating, increased copper losses, and progressive demagnetization of permanent magnets, reducing machine performance and reliability [2] - [4]. For low-speed machines such as the C-GEN, the fault-induced harmonics are often very subtle and largely obscured by the fundamental operating frequency, which complicates early detection and diagnosis [5].

This diagnostic challenge is more intense in coreless, dual-rotor PMSGs with parallel-connected coils, whose low inductance and high resistance cause a reversal of fault current distribution and weaken harmonic signatures [6] - [7]. Conventional diagnostic techniques like MCSA are commonly applied for ITSC detection. But in low speed machines, the resistive nature of the windings suppresses the amplitude of fault-related harmonics and limits the sensitivity of MCSA [8]. Alternatively, the EPVA has shown that it can detect current asymmetries caused by ITSC faults but its performance is highly dependent on fault severity and operating condition [9]. Some other methods, such as stray flux monitoring [10], physics-based back electromotive force (EMF) estimation [11], and PWM voltage-based modeling [12], have been investigated. Yet they are limited to air-cored machines such as the C-GEN, where the absence of an iron core limits their applicability.

Advanced modeling and experimental validation have helped to understand ITSC phenomena better. FEA has been widely applied to simulate the electromagnetic, thermal and harmonic behavior of PMSGs under fault conditions [13]. In addition to the simulation studies, real time monitoring algorithms combining harmonic extraction algorithms and adaptive neural networks are promising to increase the diagnostic accuracy [14]. Yet difficulties remain in distinguishing ITSC faults from other transient anomalies and evaluating their long-term impact on magnet demagnetization and machine degradation [15].

This work presents a radial-flux, dual-rotor C-GEN PMSG

with parallel-connected coils. Parallel-connected coils may introduce different fault current pathways and changes the harmonic content of the stator currents, affecting conventional diagnostic methods. This study present the analysis of ITSC fault signatures by utilizing FEA approaches. We discuss the diagnostic performance of MCSA and EPVA techniques in detecting ITSC faults in low-speed/high-pole conditions [6]- [7]. We also discuss the interplay between ITSC faults and demagnetization phenomena critical for the long-term reliability of PMSGs [16]. Recent studies in machine learning have demonstrated that data-driven methods can help fault classification and severity estimation [17]- [18] and FEA-based parameter identification techniques helped to understand fault-induced changes in electromagnetic properties [19].

This study aims to enhance ITSC fault diagnosis in radial C-GEN generators for more reliable, fault-tolerant direct drive systems in renewable energy.

II. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS (FEA) MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A model of a radial flux C-GEN generator has been developed and simulated using a FEA simulation software. A cross-sectional view of the model along with the magnetic field distribution under healthy operation is presented in Fig.1. The generator's nominal properties are given in Table I, while Table II provides a comparison between simulation results and experimental data for the same generator. The deviations observed are within acceptable limits. The electrical circuit of the ITSC has been developed in as in Fig.2, and fault severity has been defined by it's contact resistance and number of shorted turns.

Figure 1: FEA model of the C-GEN generator

Table I: Generator Properties

Rated Power(kW)	21.5
Rated Speed(rpm)	100
Stator	Coreless
Frequency(Hz)	26.67
Pole pairs	16
Stator Coils	24 x single concentrated
Stator Coil turns	205
Magnet material	N42

Table II: FEA Verification

	FEA	Experimental	Deviation(%)
Phase Voltage(V)	301.2	306.7	1.79
Phase Current(A)	17.19	17.41	1.28
Torque(Nm)	1565	1575	0.63
Electrical Power(kW)	15.5	15.4	-0.65
Mechanical Power(kW)	16.4	16.5	0.61
Efficiency(%)	94.5	93.3	-1.29

III. MATHEMATICAL MODELING

A. Radial Airgap Flux C-GEN Analysis under ITSC

The equivalent circuit of the radial flux C-GEN PMSG shown in Fig.2. In this analysis, only the phase containing the ITSC will be studied for simplicity, as ITSC-induced asymmetries are considered negligible and have no impact on the other phases, which results in the equivalent circuit presented in Fig.3. In this study, the objective is to study the effects of ITSC in C-GEN machines. Therefore, a steady-state analysis will be conducted. E_c represents the EMF of each coil, E_f represents the EMF of the faulty coil, and E_h the EMF of the healthy coil. The parameter k denotes the number of parallel-connected coils per phase, while n is the harmonic order. The rotational speed is represented by ω and stands for the rotational speed, while the short-circuit ratio is given by $\mu = \frac{N_{shorted}}{N_{total}}$ where N stands as the number of turns per coil. The contact resistance is denoted by R_{cont} . The coil resistances are defined as follows: R_h for the healthy part of the shorted coil, R_f for the shorted coil, and R_c for a coil without ITSC. Similarly, the inductances are represented as L_h for the healthy part of the shorted coil, L_f for the shorted coil and L_c for a coil without ITSC.

Figure 2: 3-Phase equivalent circuit of C-GEN under ITSC

Figure 3: Single Phase equivalent circuit of C-GEN under ITSC

Due to the strength of the magnets and the lack of an iron core, it can be assumed that $E_f = \mu \cdot E_c$ and $E_h = (1 - \mu) \cdot E_c$.

Similarly, the resistance of the coil can be expressed as $R_f = \mu \cdot R_c$ and $R_h = (1 - \mu) \cdot R_c$. The previous assumptions are not valid for the coil inductance, as the ITSC induces a mutual inductance, which must be taken into account; therefore, the steady-state analysis will be performed based on the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Simplified Single Phase equivalent circuit of C-GEN under ITSC

The mutual inductance M is given by $M = (1 - \mu) \cdot \mu \cdot P$, where P represents the permeance. The coil and load impedance are given as $Z_c = R_c + j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot L_c$ and $Z_{Load} = R_{Load} + j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot L_{Load}$ respectively. For the equivalent circuit shown in Fig.4, a mesh current analysis will be performed, while the effect of the mutual inductance will be modeled as $\Delta(\mu) = j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot M$. Parallel connected coils are symmetric, therefore mesh current analysis requires three equations. Moreover, the current of the coils that are parallel to the coil that the ITSC is taken place is given as $I_2 = \frac{I_a - I_1}{k-1}$. The resulting steady-state equations are given in eq.1, eq.2 and eq.3.

$$I_a \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k \cdot (k - 1)} \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load} \right] + I_1 \cdot \left[-\frac{1}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \right] = 2 \cdot E_c \quad (1)$$

$$I_a \cdot \left[-\frac{1}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \right] + I_1 \cdot \left[\left(\frac{k}{k - 1} - \mu \right) \cdot Z_c \right] + I_f \cdot \left[R_{cont} \right] + I_f \cdot \left[-R_{cont} - \Delta(\mu) \right] = -\mu \cdot E_c \quad (2)$$

$$I_1 \cdot \left[-R_{cont} + \Delta(\mu) \right] + I_f \cdot \left[\mu \cdot Z_c + R_{cont} \right] = \mu \cdot E_c \quad (3)$$

Solving with respect to I_a , I_1 and I_f , eq.4, eq.5 and eq.6 are obtained, where $A = -\left[\frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load} \right] \cdot Z_c \cdot \mu^2 + \frac{1}{k - 1} \cdot \left[2 \cdot Z_c + k \cdot Z_{Load} \right] \cdot \left[Z_c \cdot \mu + R_{cont} \right]$.

$$I_a = \frac{E_c \cdot \left[-\frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \cdot \mu^2 + \frac{2 \cdot k}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \cdot \mu + \frac{2 \cdot k}{k - 1} \cdot R_{cont} \right]}{A} \quad (4)$$

$$I_1 = E_c \cdot \left[\frac{-\left[\frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load} \right] \cdot \mu^2}{A} + \frac{\frac{2}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \cdot \mu + \frac{2}{k - 1} \cdot R_{cont}}{A} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$I_f = E_c \cdot \left[\frac{-\frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \cdot \mu^2 + \frac{2}{k - 1} \cdot Z_c \cdot \mu}{A} + \frac{-Z_{Load} \cdot \mu^2 + \frac{K}{k - 1} \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu + \frac{2}{k - 1} \cdot R_{cont}}{A} \right] \quad (6)$$

Equations 4-6 do not permit a determination of the evolution of each current. Therefore, in this analysis, each current will be differentiated with respect to the contact resistance and the short-circuit ratio. By examining eq.5, it is important to note that its sign can become negative when the short-circuit ratio is high and the contact resistance is low. That means that, when the fault severity is high, the current in the healthy section of the shorted coil may reverse direction. This reversal is caused by circulating currents generated between the parallel-connected coils. Furthermore, the effects of mutual inductance are neglected in this analysis for simplicity reasons and will be explained separately, as the generator operates at low speeds and features a coreless stator. Each current is differentiated with respect to the contact resistance. The results are expressed via equations 7, 8 and 9, corresponding to phase A, the healthy section of the shorted coil, and the shorted coil, respectively.

$$\frac{dI_a}{dR_{cont}} = \frac{E_c \cdot \left[\frac{k}{(k-1)^2} \cdot \mu^2 \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} \right]}{A^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dI_1}{dR_{cont}} = \frac{E_c \cdot \left[\frac{k}{k-1} \cdot \mu^2 \cdot Z_{Load}^2 + \frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k \cdot (k-1)} \cdot \mu^2 \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} \right]}{A^2} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dI_f}{dR_{cont}} = E_c \cdot \left[\frac{-\frac{k}{k-1} \cdot \left(\frac{k}{k-1} - \mu \right) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_{Load}^2}{A^2} + \frac{-\frac{k}{(k-1)^2} \cdot \left(2 - \frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k} \cdot \mu \right) \cdot \mu \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}}{A^2} \right] \quad (9)$$

For phase A, the derivative is positive, indicating that a decrease in the contact resistance leads to a reduction of the current. The same behavior is observed in the healthy section of the shorted coil: while the contact resistance decreases, the current decreases as well. In case that the fault severity is high enough to cause a current reversal in this coil, the current still decreases in a mathematical sense but increases in absolute value. In contrast, the derivative for the shorted coil is negative, meaning that while the contact resistance decreases, the current through the shorted coil increases.

Differentiating with respect to the short-circuit ratio, results in equations 10, 11 and 12 for the currents of phase A, the healthy section of the shorted coil and the shorted coil respectively.

$$\frac{dI_a}{d\mu} = E_c \cdot \left[\frac{-\frac{k}{(k-1)^2} \cdot Z_c^2 \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu^2}{A^2} + \frac{-\frac{2 \cdot k}{(k-1)^2} \cdot Z_c \cdot R_{cont} \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu}{A^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{dI_1}{d\mu} = E_c \cdot \frac{k}{k-1} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k \cdot (k-1)} \cdot Z_c + Z_{Load} \right) \cdot \frac{-Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu^2 - 2 \cdot R_{cont} \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu}{A^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dI_f}{d\mu} = E_c \cdot \frac{k}{k-1} \cdot R_{cont} \cdot \left[\frac{(k-2) \cdot Z_{Load}}{A^2} + \frac{2 \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2 \cdot k - 1}{k \cdot (k-1)} \cdot \mu\right)}{A^2} \right] \quad (12)$$

The derivative of the phase A current is negative, indicating that as the number of the shorted turns increases, the phase A current decreases. Similarly, the derivative of the current in the healthy section of the shorted coil is also negative, meaning that its current decreases with an increasing number of the shorted turns. However, if this current is negative, it will still decrease mathematically but increase in absolute value. On the other hand, the derivative of the current in the shorted coil is positive—except in the case where the contact resistance is zero. This means that, as the number of the shorted turns increases, the current in the shorted coil also increases. However, if the contact between the turns is ideal (perfect short circuit), the current in the shorted coil becomes independent of the number of the shorted turns. This is critical, as even a small number of shorted turns, that generates weak fault signatures, has the ability to cause very high currents in the shorted coil.

Another current of interest is the one flowing through the coils connected in parallel to the coil affected by ITSC. This current will be affected by the circulating currents and can be expressed as $I_2 = \frac{I_a - I_1}{k-1}$. The derivatives of this current with respect to the contact resistance and the short-circuit ratio are presented in eq.13 and eq.14 respectively.

$$\frac{dI_2}{dR_{cont}} = E_c \cdot \frac{1}{k-1} \cdot \left[\frac{-\frac{k}{k-1} \cdot \mu^2 \cdot Z_{Load}^2}{A^2} + \frac{-\frac{k^2 - 3 \cdot k + 1}{k \cdot (k-1)^2} \cdot \mu^2 \cdot Z_c \cdot Z_{Load}}{A^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{dI_2}{d\mu} = E_c \cdot \frac{k}{k-1} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{k \cdot (k-1)} \cdot Z_c - Z_{Load} \right) \cdot \frac{-Z_c \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu^2 - 2 \cdot R_{cont} \cdot Z_{Load} \cdot \mu}{A^2} \quad (14)$$

The derivative with respect to the contact resistance is negative, indicating that as the contact resistance decreases, the current increases. The derivative with respect to the short-circuit ratio is positive, meaning that an increase in the number of the shorted turns leads to an increase in the current. For this analysis, it is assumed that the load impedance Z_{Load} is greater than the coil impedance Z_c .

In the previous analysis, the effect of the mutual inductance has been neglected. In this extended model, the mutual inductance is represented as a dependent source, which is the multiplication of the corresponding current with the mutual

inductance. In the healthy section of the shorted coil, the dependent source is modeled as $-j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot M \cdot I_f$, while in the shorted coil, it is modeled as $j \cdot n \cdot \omega \cdot M \cdot I_1$.

When the contact resistance decreases, the mutual inductance remains unchanged; therefore, its effect will result solely on the variations of the current. In eq.2 the voltage induced by the mutual inductance is added to the overall EMF. As the contact resistance decreases, the current of the shorted coil increases and therefore the overall EMF will increase. This tends to increase the currents in phase A and in the healthy section of the shorted coil. However, as shown in equations 7 and 8, these currents are expected to decrease with the decrease of the contact resistance. Due to the low operating frequency, the behavior described by equations 7 and 8 dominates. As a result, the mutual inductance does not alter the trend, but instead reduces the rate at which these currents decrease as the contact resistance decreases. In eq.3, the voltage induced by the mutual inductance is subtracted from the EMF, therefore reducing it. As the contact resistance decreases, the current in the healthy section of the coil also decreases. Consequently, the reduction in the opposing mutual voltage leads to an increase in the net EMF, which in turn causes the current in the shorted coil to increase. This behavior is consistent with eq.9 and further enhances the rate at which the shorted coil current increases as the contact resistance decreases.

While the number of the shorted turns increases, the mutual inductance M initially increases, when the short-circuit ratio is less than 0.5, and begins to decrease beyond that point. Since a short-circuit ratio of 0.5 represents an extreme condition, this analysis focuses only on the more practical case where the ratio remains below 0.5. In eq.2, as the number of the shorted turns increases, the current in the shorted coil and the mutual inductance will increase. As a result, the induced voltage due to the mutual inductance also increases, therefore enhancing the EMF in this equation. This tends to increase the currents in phase A and in the healthy section of the shorted coil. However, this outcome conflicts with the predictions of equations 10 and 11, which indicate a decrease in the current. As previously discussed, due to the low operating frequency, the behavior described by equations 10 and 11 dominates. Therefore, the role of the mutual inductance in this case is to reduce the rate at which these currents decrease, rather than reversing the trend. In eq.3, as the number of the shorted turns increases, the mutual inductance also increases. However, this is counteracted by the decrease in the current through the healthy section of the coil. As a result, the induced voltage due to the mutual inductance is expected to remain relatively unchanged with an increasing short-circuit ratio. Consequently, the mutual inductance is not expected to significantly impact the current in the shorted coil as the number of shorted turns increases. This effect is more apparent in the case of an ideal short circuit.

B. Simulation Results

In low-speed machines, the coil resistance is more dominant than the coil reactance [3], as the low operating frequency

limits the effect of the coil inductance. The lack of a stator iron core removes saturation effects, keeping the induced EMF relatively unaffected and phase A current variations are insignificant. Tables III - VI support the analytical results presented in the equations 7 - 14. More specifically, Table III shows small variations consistent with equations 7 and 10, Table IV also aligns with equations 8 and 11. In case of 41 shorted turns, the current reversal can be observed. V confirms equations 13, 14, while Table VI aligns with equations 9, 12 and in case that the contact between the turns is ideal, the current in the shorted coil remains constant as the number of the shorted turns increases. Additionally, when the severity of the ITSC is low, the current of the shorted coil has small value. Finally, it can be seen in Table VII that the current of the contact resistance increases as an absolute value in the reverse direction when the fault severity increases and this is expected because $I_{\text{cont}} = I_1 - I_f$ and $I_f > I_1$.

Table III: Phase A current

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	17.1836	17.1899	17.1904	17.1904
3	17.1694	17.1856	17.1892	17.1897
5	17.1548	17.1787	17.1870	17.1885
41	16.8320	16.1957	17.0474	17.0999

Table IV: Current of the healthy part of the SC-Coil

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	4.1658	4.4046	4.4209	4.4234
3	3.6234	4.2476	4.3803	4.4013
5	3.0885	3.9900	4.3048	4.3603
41	-8.5706	-5.6434	-0.9102	1.0966

Table V: Current of parallel coils

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	4.3447	4.2673	4.2598	4.2590
3	4.5175	4.3179	4.2727	4.2659
5	4.6916	4.3991	4.2970	4.2789
41	8.4544	7.5104	5.9731	5.3399

Table VI: ITSC Coil Current

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	78.5855	10.9799	5.8342	5.1366
3	78.6130	21.0485	8.4698	6.5026
5	78.6029	28.4073	20.8887	7.8010
41	78.5226	61.7363	34.4489	23.2252

Table VII: Current of R_{contact}

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	-74.4310	-6.5828	-1.4163	-0.7510
3	-74.9909	-16.8102	-4.0953	-2.1052
5	-75.5242	-24.4266	-6.5908	-3.4457
41	-87.0788	-67.3665	-35.3263	-22.1487

IV. CURRENT BASED METHODS

A. Motor Current Signature Analysis

MCSA is among the most widely applied techniques for electrical and mechanical fault diagnosis in PMSMs, as it captures the stator current signals and analyses them in the frequency-domain. Furthermore, it can be easily implemented with low hardware cost.

Despite its advantages, MCSA has some limitations. At low speeds or with non-zero contact resistance, fault signatures may weaken or be masked by other harmonics. Variations in machine geometry, can further complicate the diagnosis by altering the harmonic patterns.

ITSC affects the impedance and the EMF of the phase, resulting to a three-phase asymmetry. As a result, the 3rd harmonic will be affected the most especially in iron cored and inverter fed machines. Since the C-GEN features a coreless stator and operates at low frequencies, the three phase asymmetries are negligible under ITSC. Table VIII and Fig.5 confirm the previous statement, as only the case with 41 shorted turns shows a noticeable increase of the 3rd harmonic.

Table VIII: MCSA 3rd harmonic

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	-74.04	-73.64	-73.58	-73.58
3	-73.05	-74.15	-73.88	-73.82
5	-70.56	-74.29	-74.25	-74.13
41	-51.01	-53.18	-58.75	-62.81

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: MCSA results for faulty cases (blue $R_{\text{cont}} = 0$, red $R_{\text{cont}} = 0.1$, orange $R_{\text{cont}} = 0.5$, purple $R_{\text{cont}} = 1$) versus the healthy (green) where: a) 1 shorted turn, b) 3 shorted turns, c) 5 shorted coils and d) 41 (20%) shorted turns.

B. Extended Park's Vector Approach

While the ITSC fault detection using the second harmonic in the Park Vector spectrum is reported to be robust via EPVA, practical measurements do not show any significant increase for low-severity - namely when only a few turns are shorted or a finite contact resistance restrains the short-circuit current. Between one and three shorted turns, the second-harmonic amplitude is barely distinguished from healthy benchmarks, as shown in the Table IX and Fig. 6. EPVA results prove to be more sensitive than the standard MCSA and the diagnostic indication is weak when the fault severity is minimal [20]. Such a surge of the fourth harmonic is measurable only at 20% fault severity (41 turns), where the observed amplitude is significantly higher than the healthy reference, which is -84.70 dB. Although EPVA theoretically can capture early stator winding faults, practical low-level ITSC conditions may produce false negatives because the second-harmonic marker is suppressed by a small short-circuit current. Thus, genuine detection of low severity faults usually requires complementary or alternative diagnostic solutions - though EPVA has been effective for more pronounced ITSC scenarios in large-scale testing [21].

Table IX: EPVA 2nd harmonic

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	-78.68	-82.40	-82.15	-82.10
3	-69.48	-81.08	-83.78	-82.75
5	-64.82	-74.90	-83.20	-83.05
41	-44.74	-47.00	-52.67	-56.76

Table X: EPVA 4th harmonic

Nshorted \ Rcont	0 (ohm)	0.1 (ohm)	0.5 (ohm)	1 (ohm)
1	-84.42	-84.02	-83.97	-83.97
3	-83.92	-84.48	-84.32	-84.17
5	-81.96	-84.73	-84.83	-84.27
41	-63.17	-65.26	-70.72	-74.74

Figure 6: EPVA results for faulty cases (blue $R_{\text{cont}} = 0$, red $R_{\text{cont}} = 0.1$, orange $R_{\text{cont}} = 0.5$, purple $R_{\text{cont}} = 1$) versus the healthy (green) where: a) 1 shorted turn, b) 3 shorted turns, c) 5 shorted coils and d) 41 (20%) shorted turns.

CONCLUSION

This study has investigated ITSC faults in a low-speed, air-cored PMSG with series and parallel-connected stator coils, by combining FEA with analytical modeling, in order to understand the impact of the contact resistance and the short-circuit ratio on the current distribution. The results effectively illustrate how each current evolves with increasing fault severity. One interesting observation is that the current in coils connected in parallel to the ITSC-affected coil exhibits significant variations. This behavior could be valuable for alternative diagnostic methods, particularly flux-based monitoring.

Additionally, traditional current based diagnostic methods such as the MCSA and EPVA have showcased challenges in the detection of ITSCs. Considering that the analysis concerns generator operation under symmetrical loading and fixed speed, field measurements may further complicate the fault diagnosis strategy.

This research highlighted the necessity for different diagnostic methods, such as the stray flux and torque monitoring. Finally, these machines are connected to the grid via power electronics and operate under continuous transients. These additional complex operating conditions are significant to be taken into consideration for future research endeavours.

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